

TABLE I - PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF HYDRAZONES (IIIa-g AND IVa-n)

Compd. no.	R ₁	M.p. °C	Yield %	N% ; Found/ (Calcd.)
R - H				
IIIa	H	221	70	10.61 (10.52)
IIIb	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	228	80	10.18 (10.16)
IIIc	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	236	76	10.23 (10.16)
IIId	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	241	90	10.21 (10.16)
IIIe	<i>p</i> -Cl	248	85	9.61 (9.69)
IIIf	<i>p</i> -Br	226	60	8.95 (8.78)
IIIg	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	237	65	13.44 (12.61)
R - CH₃				
IVa	H	185	60	9.65 (9.52)
IVb	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	176	55	9.12 (9.23)
IVc	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	155	50	9.21 (9.23)
IVd	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	165	65	9.26 (9.23)
IVe	<i>p</i> -Cl	178	63	8.65 (8.83)
IVf	<i>p</i> -Br	164	54	8.11 (8.07)
IVg	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	195	62	11.56 (11.52)
R - C₆H₅				
IVh	H	208	72	8.12 (8.34)
IVi	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	192	65	8.24 (8.12)
IVj	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	181	70	8.15 (8.12)
IVk	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	201	66	8.17 (8.12)
IVl	<i>p</i> -Cl	208	75	7.45 (7.81)
IVm	<i>p</i> -Br	188	70	7.15 (7.21)
IVn	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	210	65	10.12 (10.21)

Satisfactory C and H analysis was obtained.

p-nitro groups in the phenoxy ring [compds. no. III(f,g) and IV(f,g,m,n)] exhibited more pronounced antibacterial activity than rest of the compounds tested. It was further noticed that the introduction of acetyl or benzoyl substituted on acyclic -CO-NH- group effects a decrease in the antibacterial activity. This decrease in the activity is maximum when the benzoyl group is substituted on -CO-NH- (comps. no. IVm, n). Against *S. aureus*, all these six compounds exhibited increased activity, whereas against *B. subtilis* and *B. pumilus*, comparatively lesser antibacterial activity was observed, except compd. no. IVg which showed pronounced antibacterial activity against *B. pumilus*.

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Synthesis and Antifungal Activity of Aryloxyacetyl Hydrazones of Fluoro Aralkyl/Diaryl Ketones

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KHAN and Bahel¹ prepared fluorinated aryl hydrazones as fungicides. The -CONH-N=C= moiety of hydrazones imparts biological activities to such compounds². Various hydrazones have been reported useful as fungicides^{3,4}, bactericides⁵ and psychotropics⁶. In view of these observations, we have prepared the title hydrazones which might display significant activity due to presence of fluorine and an aryloxyacetyl moiety.

The hydrazones (III) have been obtained by the condensation of aryloxyacetyl hydrazines (I) and fluorinated aralkyl/diaryl ketones (II) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

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TABLE 1 - FUNGICIDAL DATA OF FLUOROARALKYL/DIARYL-KETO-ARYLOXYACETYL HYDRAZONES (III)

Concn.	Average % inhibition after 96 h*					
	1000 ppm	<i>A. niger</i> 100 ppm	10 ppm	1000 ppm	<i>H. oryzae</i> 100 ppm	10 ppm
Compd no.						
1	65.5	52.0	37.4	75.4	49.2	39.1
2	59.4	42.1	31.2	64.4	42.0	30.7
3	67.1	49.2	35.0	74.1	52.2	36.2
5	74.4	46.3	38.8	73.2	54.1	40.3
6	70.8	51.5	32.0	65.6	47.1	31.8
8	70.6	48.1	32.7	69.2	42.8	33.6
9	55.4	38.6	28.9	60.2	42.1	30.4
11	56.2	36.1	26.8	58.2	34.7	25.5
12	58.3	42.1	24.5	60.1	36.9	24.3
13	61.8	39.7	29.3	64.3	44.8	30.5
14	73.1	38.0	28.0	61.1	46.8	27.0
BLITOX 50 WP	94.0	81.8	75.0	96.4	91.2	81.0

* Three replications in each case.

The structures of these compounds were supported by elemental analyses, ir and nmr spectra.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were taken in Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra of the compounds were recorded in CDCl_3 solution.

Aryloxyacetyl hydrazines (I): These were prepared by the method of Conti⁷.

Fluorinated aralkyl/diaryl ketones (II): These were prepared by the method of Buu-Hoi and Xuong⁸.

Fluoroaralkyl/diaryl-keto-aryloxyacetylhydrazones (III): To a hot methanolic solution of aryloxyacetylhydrazine (0.01 M) a methanolic solution of fluoroaralkyl/diaryl ketone (0.01 M) was added dropwise with vigorous shaking. Few drops of glacial acetic acid were added and the solution refluxed on steam bath for 4 h and cooled. The solid separating out was filtered, washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol to yield the product. Compd. no. 1, R = 4-Cl-3- CH_3 . C_6H_3 , R' = C_6H_5 , (52%), m.p. 166°; ν_{max} . 3220 (broad -NH-), 1685 (-CO.NH-), 1600 (C=N), 1100 (C-F), 1050 (-C-O-C-) and 750 cm^{-1} (C-Cl) Compd. no. 2, R = 2,6-(CH_3)₂. C_6H_3 , R' = C_6H_5 , (53%), m.p. 81°. Compd. no. 3, R = 3,5-(CH_3)₂. C_6H_3 , R' = C_6H_5 , (87%), m.p. 128-129°. Compd. no. 4, R = 2,4-(CH_3)₂. C_6H_3 , R' = C_6H_5 , (56%), m.p. 84°. Compd. no. 5, R = 4-Cl-3- CH_3 . C_6H_3 , R' = C_6H_7 , (66%), m.p. 154°. Compd. no. 6, R = 2,6-(CH_3)₂. C_6H_3 , R' = C_6H_7 , (74%), m.p. 180°; ν_{max} 3250 (broad -NH-), 1740 (-CO.NH-), 1650 (C=N), 1035 (-C-O-C-) and 745 cm^{-1} (1,2,3-trisubstituted benzene). Compd. no. 7, R = 3,5-(CH_3)₂. C_6H_3 , R' = C_6H_7 , (57%), m.p. 65°. Compd. no. 8, R = 2,4-(CH_3)₂. C_6H_3 , R' = C_6H_7 , (72%), m.p. 93°. Compd. no. 9, R = 4-Cl-3- CH_3 . C_6H_3 , R' = C_6H_5 , (77%), m.p. 101°. Compd. no. 10, R = 2,6-(CH_3)₂. C_6H_3 , R' = C_6H_5 , (76%), m.p. 60°. Compd. no. 11, R

= 3,5-(CH_3)₂. C_6H_3 , R' = C_6H_5 , (95%), m.p. 88°; ν_{max} 3200 (broad -NH-), 1680 (-CO.NH-), 1650 (C=N), 1130 (C-F) and 1035 cm^{-1} (-C-O-C-); δ 1.7 (s, 9H, CH_3), 2.8 (s, 2H, -CO. CH_2), 6.4 (b, 1H, =N.NH), 7.8 (m, 11H, aromatic protons). Compd. no. 12, R = 2,4-(CH_3)₂. C_6H_3 , R' = C_6H_5 , (97%), m.p. 100°. Compd. no. 13, R = 3,5-(CH_3)₂. C_6H_3 , R' = 4-Cl. C_6H_4 , (91%), m.p. 112°. Compd. no. 14, R = 2,4-(CH_3)₂. C_6H_3 , R' = 4-Cl. C_6H_4 , (70%), m.p. 162°. The elemental analyses of the above compounds were found to be within satisfactory limits.

Fungicidal screening: Eleven compounds were evaluated for their antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *H. oryzae* by agar plate technique⁹ at concentrations 1000, 100 and 10 ppm. The fungicidal activity displayed by compounds has been given in Table 1. A commercial fungicide BLITOX 50 WP was also tested under similar conditions to compare the result.

Results and Discussion

Most of the compounds have significant fungitoxicity at 1000 and 100 ppm against both the fungi but their fungicidal action decreased upon dilution. Although the compounds no. 1, 3, 5, inhibit > 35% of the growth of both the test organisms even at 10 ppm, the results are not so spectacular as one may expect due to the presence of fluorine and aryloxyacetyl moiety.

It is further revealed that compounds with 4-chloro-3-methyl moiety are relatively more potent. Compounds having 3,5-dimethyl groups are more fungitoxic than those with methyl groups at other positions in benzene nucleus. In general, fluoro-benzophenone hydrazones are less fungitoxic than the corresponding fluoropropiophenone/butyrophenone hydrazones.

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Synthesis and Mercuration of Some New 2-Arylimino-4-oxazolidones as Pesticides

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CHEMISTRY¹ and wide range of pharmacological²⁻⁴ properties of oxazolidones have been cited in the literature. In the present work an attempt has been made to synthesise some new 2-arylimino-4-oxazolidones (Ia and Ib) by condensing different monoaryl ureas with chloroacetic acid and α -chloropropionic acid separately in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in absolute ethanol medium.

Structure Ia of the compound has been established from the characteristic ir peaks at 1560 (N-C-O), 3260 (NH) and 1742 cm⁻¹ (C=O five membered β -lactum ring⁵), and pmr peaks at τ 5.8 (2H, s), 5.2 (1H, br, s) and 2.6 (4H, s) due to -CH₂- at 5-position of the ring, -NH-, and aromatic protons, respectively. Structure Ib was confirmed from ir peaks at 1560 (N-C-O), 3260 (NH) and 1742 cm⁻¹ (C=O), and pmr peaks at τ 5.6 (1H, s), 8.2 (3H, m), 5.2 (1H, br, m) and 2.6 (4H, s) assigned to -CH- at 5-position of the

ring, CH₃- at C₅ position, -NH- and aromatic protons, respectively with tetramethylsilane as internal standard. It was further substantiated from the reported⁶ sulphur analogue, 2-arylimino-4-thiazolidones under the similar experimental condition.

Further, Ia and Ib were mercurated by one equivalent of mercuric acetate with a view to enhance their pesticidal activity. Acetoxymercuri group usually enters into the para position⁷ of N-phenyl nucleus if it is free, otherwise occupies the ortho position of the same nucleus. The position of acetoxymercuri group is further justified from the fact that 2-imino-4-oxazolidone synthesised from urea and chloroacetic acid is never mercurated under these experimental conditions. The final evidence for the position of acetoxymercuri group comes from the following observations.

Monoacetoxymercuri compound, IIa was treated with sodium perbromide to yield compound IIIa, which was identical with 2-(p-bromophenyl)-imino-4-oxazolidone synthesised independently from p-bromophenylurea and chloroacetic acid. The identity of the two compounds were established through superimposable ir curve, identical R_f value by tlc and undepressed m.m.p.

Experimental

2-Phenylimino-4-oxazolidone (Ia): Phenyl urea (0.05 mol) was refluxed with chloroacetic acid (0.05 mol) in presence of sodium acetate (3.5 g) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) on a boiling water bath for 20 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into cold water and the precipitate washed with hot water. It was crystallised from rectified spirit to yield the product (80%), m.p. 207° (Found: N, 15.70. C₉H₈O₂N₂ requires N, 15.90%).

2-(p-Acetoxymercuriphenyl) imino-4-oxazolidone (IIa): 2-Phenylimino-4-oxazolidone (0.01 mol) in acetic acid-ethanol (1 : 1, 10 ml) was treated with a solution of mercuric acetate (0.01 mol) in acetic